

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Effectiveness of Classroom Management at Sekolah Menengah Kejuruan (SMK) in Sulawesi Selatan, Indonesia.

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ABSTRACT

One indicator that states that teachers (educators) are professional is the ability to manage the class. This study aims to describe the effectiveness of class management in class X students at Vocational high School (Indonesia: *Sekolah Menengah Kejuruan / SMK*) Country 1 Maros. This research is a quantitative descriptive. The study population was all students of State Senior High School 1 Maros class X, totaling 462 students, because of the large population, this study conducted 10 percent sampling so that a sample of 46 people was obtained. The techniques used in data collection are observation, questionnaires, interviews, and documentation. Data analysis is presented through a frequency table and processed through a score calculation technique. The data analysis technique in this study uses the percentage formula. The results of this study indicate that the effectiveness of class management in class X students at SMK Country 1 Maros has been carried out very effectively with a percentage of 81.54%. These results are seen from three indicators, namely; 1) the physical condition in the very effective category with a percentage of 84.35%, 2) the socio-emotional condition in the very effective category with a percentage of 85.51%, 3) the organizational condition in the effective category with a percentage of 72.90%.

Keywords: *Teacher, Classroom management, Students.*

INTRODUCTION

Education has a fairly broad meaning, depending on who interprets it; in what context, what scope, what level. Education can be interpreted as an effort to educate the nation, instill moral and religious values, build personality, teach knowledge, train skills, provide guidance, direction, guidance, role model, discipline, and so on. (Abbas, Nichol, & Wong, 2018; Musfah, 2015; Saleh & Arhas, 2019; Suprianto, Arhas, & Salam, 2018). The main requirement that must be met for an effective and efficient learning process to take place is the availability of teachers (educators) who can fulfill effective classroom management. Classroom management is a complex behavior problem, and teachers (educators) so that

the learning process can run well and with quality. The quality of the process and optimal learning outcomes requires teachers who can manage the class (Bru, Stephens, & Torsheim, 2002; Cristea, 2015; George & Lal, 2019; Saban, 2009).

One indicator that states that teachers (educators) are professional is the ability to manage the class, which is to provide a conducive atmosphere for an effective and efficient learning process. If it is not yet conducive, then a teacher (educator) must make every effort to master, organize and improve, and create a conducive classroom atmosphere so that the learning process can run optimally to achieve the desired learning goals (Hamran, 2017; Muslimin, Saleh, & Darwis, 2020; Sukmawati, 2017)

According to (Suharsimi, 2013), Class management is an effort made by the person in charge of the intended learning activities to achieve conducive and optimal conditions so that learning activities can be carried out as expected. According to (Emmer & Stough, 2001), Classroom management is defined as 1) teacher behavior that can produce high student achievement due to active student involvement in class. 2) student behavior that does not interfere much with the activities of teachers and other students. 3) use an efficient learning time.

According to (Hosnan, 2014) Classroom management is an effort made by the teacher to condition the class by optimizing various sources (potential in the teacher, facilities, learning environment in the classroom) which are intended so that the teaching and learning process can run according to the planning goals to be achieved. Based on the expert opinion above, it can be concluded that classroom management is an activity planned by the teacher to achieve an effective and efficient learning process.

After making observations at the research location, it was found that there were problems, including learning conditions that were not optimal due to inadequate classroom conditions such as unfit chairs, unavailability of fans in some classes, the unsuitable number of chairs, and the number of students, only a few classes had lights. still functioning, there are still some empty classes during class hours, there are teachers who take additional hours outside of normal class hours, use monotonous teaching methods, and so on.

METHOD

The variable in this study was a single variable, namely the effectiveness of class management in class X students at SMK Country 1 Maros. This research is a descriptive study that seeks to describe it carefully, clearly, and objectively. To measure this variable using a questionnaire instrument (questionnaire) using an ordinal scale arranged based on variable indicators. According to (Arikunto, 2019) The population is the whole research subject, the population in this study were 462 respondents. The sample is a part or representative of the population under study or part of the subject representing the entire population (Universum). This sampling is done so that the collection of data or samples will be relatively much shorter, lighter, and cheaper than collecting the entire population with a total of 46 respondents. The data collection techniques used in this study were observation, questionnaires, interviews, and documentation.

An activity that is quite important in the entire research process is data processing. With data processing, it can be seen about the meaning of the data that has been collected so that the research results will be immediately known. The data analysis technique used in this study was a descriptive analysis design, for that data analysis technique used was percentage analysis by presenting each question to determine the effectiveness of class management in class X students at SMK Country 1 Maros.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Data regarding the effectiveness of classroom management was obtained through a questionnaire instrument as the main technique in data collection in the study, then the presentation and processing of data were carried out using frequency and percentage tables. Physical conditions are measured based on the sub-indicators of the space where the teaching and learning process takes place, seating arrangements, ventilation, and lighting arrangements, storage arrangements for items which are then described through 5 (five) statement items.

Based on the results of presenting data from each indicator starting from physical conditions, socio-emotional conditions, and organizational conditions, where the three indicators as a whole can be seen as the results of data analysis in the tables and graphs below.:

Physical condition

The purpose of physical conditions here means that the conditions seen from the learning environment can support the increasing intensity of the student's learning process on a positive effect on teaching objectives. The results of the effectiveness of classroom management for indicators of physical conditions can be seen as a whole in Table 1:

Table 1.
Data Analysis based on Physical Condition Indicators

No.	Sub Indicator	n	N	%	Category
1	Space where the teaching and learning process takes place	197	230	85,65	Very effective
2	Seating arrangement	202	230	87,82	Very effective
3	Ventilation and light regulation	402	460	87,39	Very effective
4	Storage arrangements	169	230	73,47	Effective
Total		970	1150	84,35	Very effective

Source: Results of Data Processing

To determine the effectiveness of classroom management at SMK Country 1 Maros, it can be seen from the indicators of physical conditions and can be measured using the following formula:

$$\% = \frac{n}{N} \times 100$$

$$\begin{aligned} \% &= \frac{970}{1150} \times 100 \\ &= 84,35\% \end{aligned}$$

The results of the data analysis show that the value for the indicator of initiative in completing work is 84.35 percent. When consulted with measurement standards, the value of 84.35 percent is in the very effective category.

Based on the results of research through questionnaires and observations made by researchers, it is evident that the physical conditions in class management in class X students at Smk Country 1 Maros have been achieved very very effectively. This is supported by the results of data analysis on the physical condition indicators described in 5 (five) statements, which state that classroom management in physical conditions has been achieved with a percentage rate of 84.35 percent and is in a very effective category.

Socio-Emotional Conditions

The socio-emotional condition in question is where the condition can influence the teaching and learning process. The results of the effectiveness of classroom management for indicators of socio-emotional conditions can be seen as a whole in Table 2:

Table 2.

Data Analysis based on Socio-Emotional Indicators

No.	Sub Indicator	n	N	%	Category
1	Leadership type	204	230	88,70	Very effective
2	Teacher's attitude	190	230	82,61	Very effective
3	Teacher's voice	196	230	85,22	Very effective
Total		590	690	85,51	Very effective

Source: Results of Data Processing

To determine the effectiveness of classroom management at SMK Country 1 Maros, it can be seen from the indicators of socio-emotional conditions and can be measured using the following formula:

$$\begin{aligned} \% &= \frac{n}{N} \times 100 \\ &= \frac{590}{690} \times 100 \\ &= 85,51\% \end{aligned}$$

The results of the data analysis show that the value for the Prakarsa indicator in completing work is 85.51 percent. The socio-emotional condition in question is where the condition can influence the teaching and learning process. Based on the results of research through questionnaires and observations made by researchers, it was proven that the socio-emotional conditions in class management in class X students at SMK Country 1 Maros were in a very very effective category. This is supported by the results of data analysis on the indicators of socio-emotional conditions described in 3 (three) statements, which state

that classroom management in socio-emotional conditions has been achieved with a percentage level of 85.51 percent and is in the very effective category.

Organizational Conditions

To see the results of the effectiveness of class management for indicators of organizational conditions, it can be seen as a whole in Table 3:

Table. 3

Data Analysis based on Organizational Condition Indicators

No.	Sub Indicator	n	N	%	Category
1	Replacement lessons	162	230	70,43	Effective
2	Teachers who were unable to attend	146	230	63,48	Effective
3	Problems between students	195	230	84,78	Effective
Total		503	690	72,90	Effective

Source: Results of Data Processing

To determine the effectiveness of class management at SMK Country 1 Maros, it can be seen from the indicators of organizational conditions and can be measured using the following formula:

$$\begin{aligned} \% &= \frac{n}{N} \times 100 \\ \% &= \frac{503}{690} \times 100 \\ &= 72,90\% \end{aligned}$$

The results of the data analysis show that the value for the Prakarsa indicator in completing work is 72.90 percent, so the value for 72.90 percent is Effective.

$$\% = \frac{\text{the number of values obtained}}{\text{number of items} \times \text{ideal score} \times \text{number of respondents}} \times 100\%$$

$$\% = \frac{n}{N} \times 100\%$$

$$\% = \frac{2063}{2530} \times 100\%$$

$$= 81,54\%$$

Organizational Conditions

Organizational conditions mean conditions that are done to prevent problems in class management with good habits and regular behavior that are embedded in students. Based on the results of research through questionnaires and observations made by researchers, it is evident that the organizational conditions in the management of class X students at SMA Country 1 Maros have been achieved effectively. This is supported by the results of data analysis on respondents' answers to the indicators of organizational conditions described

in 3 (three) statements, which state that students have been reached with a percentage level of 72.90 percent and are in the effective category.

DISCUSSION

Physical condition

The physical environment in which to learn has an important influence on the results of learning actions. The purpose of physical conditions here means that the conditions seen from the learning environment can support the increasing intensity of the student's learning process on a positive influence on teaching goals starting from the room where the teaching and learning process takes place, seating arrangements, ventilation and lighting arrangements, and storage arrangements for goods. -goods.

According to (Rohani & Ahmadi, 2015) The physical environment includes the space where the teaching and learning process takes place, seating arrangements, classroom ventilation, classroom lighting, and storage arrangements. To create good physical conditions, all of these indicators need to be fulfilled to be able to make students comfortable in participating in the teaching and learning process.

Socio-Emotional Conditions

The socio-emotional conditions in the classroom will have a considerable influence on the teaching and learning process. The socio-emotional condition referred to is where the conditions can influence the teaching and learning process including the type of leadership, teacher attitudes, and teacher's voice. As said by (Rohani & Ahmadi, 2015) that to improve the socio-emotional condition three indicators are needed, namely the type of leadership, teacher attitudes, and teacher's voice. The type of leadership is one of the indicators that need to be fulfilled because the type of leadership will help create a favorable climate for the creation of optimal teaching and learning conditions, students will learn productively both when supervising the teacher and without being supervised by the teacher. In this condition, the problem of class management is usually limited as little as possible.

Meanwhile, the attitude of the teacher needs to be considered to deal with students who violate school rules and should remain patient, and remain friendly can be improved. If the teacher is forced to hate, hate the student's behavior, and not hate the student. And finally, a teacher, this is important because it will attract the attention of students, a voice that is too shrill will not be liked by students while a voice that is too low is the same.

Organizational Conditions

Routine activities that are organized both at the class level and at the school level will be able to prevent classroom management problems, with routine activities that have been clearly regulated and have been communicated to all students openly so that it is clear to them, will cause it to become embedded in every student. good habits and regularity of behavior. Organizational conditions are defined as conditions that are carried out to prevent problems in class management with good habits and regular behavior that are embedded in students. Activities that cover organizational according to (Rohani &

Ahmadi, 2015) namely replacement of lesson hours, teachers who were unable to attend, and problems between students.

In this indicator, the role of students will be more dominant because students need to know themselves first and then decide to take an action. In this process, students are also expected to be able to solve their problems with a good mindset, not by making riots or actions that violate the rules.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion, the results of the study concluded that the effectiveness of classroom management in class X students at SMK Country 1 Maros was in the "Very Effective" category. This can prove that at SMK Country 1 Maros, class management in class X students has met physical conditions, socio-emotional conditions, and organizational conditions. The effectiveness of class management in class X students at SMK Country 1 Maros can be seen from 3 (three) aspects that are assessed, namely: Physical conditions are categorized as very effective, socio-emotional conditions are categorized as very effective, and organizational conditions are categorized as effective.

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